

energy conformation of the protonated form of 5-HDA is : 17.98⁸.

TABLE 1—5-HYDROXY DOPAMINE : TOTAL OVERLAP POPULATIONS BETWEEN BONDED ATOMS—CNDO/2

Atoms	TOP
Cl-C2	0.9524
Cl-C6	0.9497
Cl-C7	0.7211
C2-C3	0.9594
C2-H2	0.7565
C3-C4	0.9588
C3-O1	0.6067
C4-C5	0.9520
C4-O2	0.5878
C5-C6	0.9540
C5-O3	0.6445
C6-H6	0.7543
C7-C8	0.7249
C7-H71	0.7000
C7-H72	0.7244
C8-N	0.5716
C8-H81	0.7201
C8-H82	0.7543
N-HN1	0.6810
N-HN2	0.6704
N-HN3	0.6477
O1-HO1	0.6446
O2-HO2	0.6271
O3-HO3	0.6692

It may be of interest to mention in this connection that the global minimum energy by PCILO method was obtained at $\tau_1 \approx 56^\circ$ and $\tau_2 \approx 40^\circ$ for :-HDA. The PCILO dipolemoment for this conformation is : 34.4858 D and agrees well with that of CNDO/2 value : 34.4995 D.

The gross atomic populations (GAP's) obtained by PCILO method are indicated within the parentheses (Fig. 2).

It is to be noted that the PCILO-GAP's more or less resemble the CNDO/2 results, and there is reasonable agreement between the CNDO/2 and PCILO GAP's on the N-atom. The positively-charged nitrogen in the side-chain ammonium group is one of the most active points for biological and pharmacological activities of the protonated molecules.

The work reported here represents a part of the work in progress. The allowed region for 6-hydroxy dopamine (6-HDA) has already been determined³ by PCILO method⁴. The CNDO/2 calculations on 6-HDA and its oxidation product (quinone form) are in progress. Quantum chemical calculations solve the conformational problems and charge distributions of 5-HDA and the biogenic amine NE (nor-epinephrine) can help to find a new insight into the mechanism of replacement of NE by this molecule (5-HDA). It has been shown² that 5-HDA may intrude into the pathways of NE.

Acknowledgements

This work was performed while the author was on leave for six months and was appointed as a part time visiting Assistant Professor, Anesthesiology, in the Johns Hopkins University (JHU), Baltimore, Maryland, U.S.A. I should like to acknowledge especially the generosity of Prof. W. S. Koski and Dr. Joyce J. Kaufman of JHU, Department of Chemistry for providing computational and other necessary facilities during my stay at the Johns Hopkins University, as well as stimulating discussions with Dr. Joyce J. Kaufman. I wish to convey my sincere thanks to Dr. H. J. T. Preston of JHU for his kind help in computation of the above work. Special thanks are also due to Mr. K. R. Guha and Mrs. Aurora P. Guha for their constant encouragement and help in various ways during my stay in U. S. A. for the completion of this work.

References

1. J. A. POPLE and D. L. BEVERIDGE) Approximate Molecular Orbital Theory (McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1970).
2. J. P. TRANZER and H. THOENEN, *Experientia*, 1967, 23, 743.
3. SEPHALI GUHA, Details to be published shortly.
4. S. DINER, J. P. MALRIEU, F. JORDAN and M. GILBERT, *Theoret. Chim. Acta. (Berl.)*, 1969, 15, 100.
5. A.M. ANDERSON, A. MOSTAD and CHR. ROMMING, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1972, 26, 2670.
6. JOYCE J. KAUFMAN, *Intern. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1971, 48, 205.
7. W. GIORDANO, J. R. HAMANN, J. J. HARKINS and JOYCE J. KAUFMAN, *Mol. Pharmacol.*, 1967, 3, 307.
8. JOYCE J. KAUFMAN, *Intern. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1967, 1S, 485.

Some Newer Cyanoethylated Cyanoacetanilides as Possible Insecticides*

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Manuscript received 5 May 1976, revised 14 October 1976
accepted 12 January 1977

THE studies on cyanoethylation reaction as reported earlier from the laboratory,^{1,2,3} have been further extended to synthesize some newer substituted cyanoethyl-cyanoacetanilides. In the present investigation these compounds have been tested for their insecticidal activity on adult housefly.

Experimental

Cyanoethylation of Cyanoacetanilides to α -cyano- α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) acetanilides.

A mixture of cyanoacetanilide (2 g), dioxane (20 ml) and benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (1.3 ml) was stirred. Acrylonitrile (1.9 g) was added slowly with

*Contributed on 65th Birthday of Professor H. Kammerer, W. Germany.

TABLE I—CYANOETHYLATION OF CYANOACETANILIDES TO α , CYANO α , α -BIS-(β -CYANOETHYL) ACETANILIDES

(R)	M.P. °C	Yield	Mol. formula	Carbon		Hydrogen		Nitrogen	
				F	R	F	R	F	R
4-Cl	155	75	C ₁₅ H ₉ ON ₄ Cl	59.10	59.90	40.30	40.30	18.54	18.63
2-Cl	104-05	85	C ₁₅ H ₉ ON ₄ Cl	59.91	59.9	40.34	40.32	18.71	18.63
4-CH ₃	260-62	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₄	62.12	67.1	5.71	5.70	20.0	20.0
3-CH ₃	248-49	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₄	67.14	67.1	5.71	5.70	20.1	20.0
4-OCH ₃	215-17	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄	64.90	64.87	5.41	5.40	18.73	18.90
3-r	248	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ BrO	52.2	52.17	3.81	3.77	16.18	16.23
4-NO ₂	208-10	80	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄	57.9	57.67	4.17	4.18	22.42	22.50
3-NO ₂	85-86	55	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄	57.89	57.87	4.2	4.18	22.45	22.50
2-NO ₂	205-06	50	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄	57.89	57.87	4.21	4.18	22.52	22.50

cooling. The stirring was continued for 5 hours 30-35°. The solution was neutralised with dil. hydrochloric acid and poured into ice water. The solid thus separated was recrystallized from ethanol into colourless crystals, m.p. 150°; yield, 2.8g (40%). Found N, 20.97%; C, 67.86%; H, 5.20%. C₁₅H₉N₄O required, N, 21.05%; C, 67.67%; H, 5.20%.

Similarly other substituted cyanoacetanilides were prepared by the above method. They are given in table I.

Results and Discussion

Only five compounds were tested in α cyano- α , α -bis (β -cyanoethyl, acetanilide series). They did not show any significant insecticidal activity on adult housefly. A comparative study of the insecticidal activity of these cyanoethylated cyanoacetanilides, malonanilides, ethyl malonates and their derivatives will be described elsewhere.

Acknowledgements

The author wishes to thank Dr. Nitya Anand Director, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow and Tata Pesticides Division, Bangalore for analysis and biological activity of the compounds respectively.

References

- G. S. MISRA and J. S. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 29, 455.
- J. S. SHUKLA and R. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 572.
- J. S. SHUKLA and R. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 375.

Heteropoly-Niobate and Tantalate Containing Vanadium(V)

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Manuscript received 5 August 1976, revised 1 December 1976, accepted 30 December 1976

THE present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of two new heteropoly salts of niobium and tantalum containing vanadium as the hetero atom. Previous reports^{1,2} on such studies are only a few.

Aqueous solutions of freshly prepared³ and analysed potassium hexaniobate, K₇HfNb₆O₁₉·13H₂O, and potassium metavanadate were taken in the molar ratio of 12 : 1 and refluxed for 6 hr. in a round bottom flask provided with a series of potash bulb guard tubes which absorbed CO₂ from air. Thus hydrolysis of alkali metal hexaniobate, due to the presence of atmospheric CO₂, was easily avoided. The refluxed solution was then left in atmosphere for three days and finally crystallised under vacuum when light yellow needle shaped crystals came out which were recrystallised thrice from hot water. For analysis of the compound, vanadium was estimated colorimetrically by hydrogen peroxide method⁴. Niobium was estimated gravimetrically⁵ by precipitating it as niobic acid with conc. HCl and then weighing as Nb₂O₅ at 850°. Hydrogen was estimated by element estimation technique (Found: K, 15.32; V, 1.97; Nb, 44.27; H, 1.59 percent. Calcd. for K₁₂H [VNB₁₂O₄₈]20H₂O : K, 15.44; V, 2.01; Nb, 44.15; H, 1.61 percent). The final representation